

Knowledge-Based Risk Assessment: A GeoKG Framework for Vector-Borne Disease ABMs

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Abstract

Vector-borne disease risk emerges from interacting climatic, social, and demographic factors, yet current approaches often flatten this complexity through semantically thin, layer-based environments. We propose a workflow integrating Geospatial Knowledge Graphs (GeoKGs) into epidemiological agent-based models (ABMs), using *Aedes albopictus* and dengue as a use case. The GeoKG specifies the habitat conditions of the model environment, exposed to the ABM as a hexagonal (H3) grid with ontology-derived per-cell attributes; transmission dynamics and final risk emerge from the ABM. The approach offers three improvements: (1) explicit semantics for the habitat representation, (2) ontology reusability across study areas, and (3) model input traceability. The scope is restricted to the Exposure \times Hazard components of risk. A proof of concept instantiates the full pipeline for GBIF *Aedes albopictus* records in France. Next steps include further data input and validation against vector occurrence data independent of those used in the graph construction.

Keywords: agent-based model, spatial simulation, GAMA

1. Introduction

In recent years, several European countries, like Spain, France, Italy or Croatia, have reported increasing numbers of autochthonous dengue cases (ECDC 2026, Farooq et al. 2025). Dengue is a vector-borne disease (VBD) that is transmitted via mosquitoes, e.g., the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*). The expanding geographical range of dengue outbreaks and tiger mosquito

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium. This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

occurrences in temperate Europe places new demands on health authorities and decision-makers, particularly with respect to spatially explicit risk assessment. With increasing numbers of locally acquired dengue cases in Europe, the historical framing of dengue as a tropical disease no longer matches reality and requires action now.

Disease modelling has a long tradition in mathematics and statistics, and spatially explicit risk assessment has traditionally relied on weighted overlay methods that combine environmental layers into a composite risk surface. These approaches treat risk as an aggregated, largely static property of a location and leave little room for individual behaviour, heterogeneity, or feedback between hosts, vectors, and environment. Agent-based models (ABMs) gained traction in epidemiological modelling during the 2010s (Maneerat & Daudé 2016, Mahmood et al. 2020) as a response to these limitations. However, Morrison et al. (2024) found that scenario-based modelling is still lagging, though needed in epidemiology. ABMs offer several benefits for epidemiological modelling as entities, e.g., humans and vectors, with attributes such as health status, movement type, or feeding behaviour, exist as individuals that can interact with each other and their environment (O'Sullivan & Perry 2013). For a vector-borne disease such as dengue, this individual-based perspective is valuable. The transmission of a vector-borne disease requires spatial co-location of infected vectors and susceptible hosts. As a result, the spatial dimension is not merely contextual but constitutive of the process itself. Local interactions at the individual level can give rise to emergent behaviour at the system level. Incorporating the environment adds further drivers, e.g., temperature, rainfall, proximity to breeding sites, that condition *where* and *when* transmissions occur. Therefore, the strength of a spatially explicit ABM is not the complexity it introduces, but its capacity to represent the heterogeneity that shapes disease dynamics. However, one question remains a recurring problem in ABMs: how can environmental context be represented in a way that is both transparent and transferable across regions? While the host–virus–vector mechanism and transmission probabilities remain the same across settings, the environmental context does not, and models calibrated for one region rarely transfer cleanly to another.

Neither tradition currently answers that well. Mathematical models leave out the spatial component of virus transmission. Weighted overlay maps collapse heterogeneous risk factors into composite values whose weighting choices are rarely traceable. ABMs typically draw on raster or vector inputs that treat each thematic layer as an isolated value, without encoding the semantic relationships between features. A further, well-known limitation concerns the sensitivity of results to the choice of spatial unit, formalised as the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP; Openshaw 1984): both resolution and zoning can substantially affect model outcomes, yet in raster-based ABMs this sensitivity is typically left implicit in the design choice of pixel size (Wöhs & Wallentin 2026). Another limitation lies in the model documentation: the ODD (Overview, Design concepts, Details) protocol (Grimm et al. 2020) provides a standardised description of ABMs, but it is a narrative document, not a machine-readable specification. As a result, neither the environmental inputs nor the model logic are queryable or transferable to new areas of interest without substantial manual re-implementation.

Geospatial Knowledge Graphs (GeoKGs) offer a way to address these limitations. By representing geographic entities, their attributes, and their relationships within formal, machine-interpretable graph structures, they render environmental context explicit and queryable, and support its reuse across study areas (Janowicz et al. 2022, Scheider et al. 2019). Initiatives such as

KnowWhereGraph demonstrate this potential for integrating heterogeneous environmental and social data at scale (Janowicz et al. 2022). Recent work has begun to apply GeoKGs to ecological and epidemiological problems. Xiao et al. (2025) applied GeoKGs for habitat suitability assessment, and Consoli et al. (2025) developed the *eKG* (epidemiological knowledge graph) based on WHO Disease Outbreak News. To our knowledge, however, no GeoKG has yet been coupled with an ABM for spatially explicit vector-borne disease risk modelling.

This paper proposes a preliminary workflow that addresses this gap. We design a GeoKG-informed environment for an ABM of *Aedes albopictus*-mediated dengue transmission, in which the GeoKG acts as a semantic pre-processing layer for the vector habitat input. The approach offers three improvements over conventional environments: (1) explicit, ontology-driven semantics for habitat area definitions; (2) reusability of the ontology across areas of interest; and (3) traceability of model inputs, making missing data and the associated input uncertainty explicit. Our scope is restricted to the Exposure \times Hazard components of risk, for now; vulnerability indicators are reserved for future work.

2. Methodology

2.1. Workflow Overview

The proposed workflow couples a GeoKG with an ABM through a semantic pre-processing layer. Heterogeneous geospatial data are lifted into an ontologically structured knowledge graph, discretised onto a hexagonal grid, and exposed to the ABM as an attributed environment. Figure 1 illustrates the overall risk model architecture, including four main stages of the GeoKG integration: (1) ingestion of geospatial data from authoritative environmental, demographic, and ecological sources; (2) semantic lifting into RDF using established vocabularies; (3) projection of the integrated data onto a discrete global grid system (DGGS) to produce grid-indexed attribute tables; and (4) ingestion of these tables as the environmental grid of an ABM implemented in the GAMA platform (Taillandier et al. 2019).

Figure 1. Proposed workflow of GeoKG and ABM coupling for VBD risk modelling.

A central design principle is the separation of concerns between the GeoKG and the ABM: The GeoKG handles input semantics, integration, and provenance; the ABM handles behavioural logic and generative processes. This separation allows the ontology to be developed, validated, and reused independently of any specific simulation, while the ABM remains agnostic to the source data formats it consumes. A proof of concept (PoC) instantiates the architecture for a single data layer, i.e., GBIF occurrence records of *Aedes albopictus* in France, with further layers (climate, land use, population density) accommodated by the schema but reserved for subsequent iterations. The transmission risk itself emerges from the simulation runs via a Monte-Carlo approach.

2.2. Data Sources and Risk Factors

The workflow draws on three categories of risk factors aligned with the Exposure \times Hazard components of vector-borne disease risk. *Environmental* variables describe vector habitat conditions (e.g., ERA5 temperature and precipitation, CORINE land cover, Sentinel-2 NDVI). *Demographic* variables describe host populations (e.g., GHSL settlement and population density). *Ecological* variables describe vector presence, sourced from species occurrence records (e.g., GBIF). *Behavioural* risk factors related to human mobility are conceptually included in the schema but reserved for a later development stage. Within the Exposure \times Hazard framing, hazard is constituted primarily by environmental and ecological variables (habitat suitability for the vector), while exposure is represented through demographic variables (host availability) and the mechanic exposure of individual agents in the ABM. The PoC reported here instantiates only the ecological/vector-presence component using GBIF records for France.

2.3. Ontology Design and Knowledge Graph Construction

The PoC graph reuses established vocabularies rather than introducing a bespoke disease ontology at this stage. Darwin Core represents occurrence records, taxa, and sampling events; GeoSPARQL encodes geometries as WKT-typed `geo:Point` literals; Dublin Core terms cover licensing and provenance. Each GBIF record yields an Occurrence node linked to a shared Taxon node for *Aedes albopictus*, an Event node carrying temporal attributes, and a Location node bearing the geometry and administrative context (state/province, county, municipality, GADM levels). The graph is constructed with `rdflib` and serialised to Turtle; SPARQL queries against the in-memory graph verify integrity, and the serialisation is additionally loaded into GraphDB Free for visual exploration. A unified disease ontology aligning vector ecology (Xiao et al. 2025) with epidemiological structure (Consoli et al. 2025) is the target for subsequent iterations; the present vocabulary is the minimum subset required to support the discretisation and ABM-handover steps.

2.4. Spatial Discretisation and ABM Integration

To bridge the GeoKG and the ABM, the knowledge graph is projected onto a hexagonal discrete global grid system. Hexagonal cells offer uniform adjacency with six neighbours at equal distance, in contrast to the von Neumann and Moore neighbourhoods of rectangular grids. The hierarchical multi-resolution property is also relevant for handling MAUP effects: spatial discretisation becomes an explicit, parametrisable component of the model, allowing scale effects to be studied systematically rather than masked by a single resolution choice. The specific DGGS implementation is treated as interchangeable; the relevant property is the hexagonal, hierarchical indexing scheme rather than a particular system. The PoC uses Uber's H3 at a resolution auto-

selected from the median GBIF coordinate uncertainty. Each occurrence is assigned to an H3 cell and aggregated into a grid-indexed table; this table, together with a shapefile of the cell geometries (Figure 2), is exported to GAMA, where cells are instantiated as `hex_cell` agents and serve as the environmental grid of the ABM. Human agents are distributed proportionally to the per-cell occurrence count for the PoC; mosquito and human agents access the attributes of the cells they occupy at each timestep. The transmission logic with 8h timesteps, S-I-R dengue dynamics, mosquito extrinsic incubation period, gonotrophic cycle, and dispersal is inherited from an earlier raster-based version of the model and adapted here to operate on the H3 cell agents (Wöhs & Wallentin 2026). A consequence of this design is that the *what* of the model environment is specified by the ontology and the corresponding query, not by the ABM code: two simulations of the same model logic, run over different areas of interest or with different sets of input variables, differ only in the GeoKG query, not in the ABM implementation. This is the mechanism by which the workflow is designed to operationalise the transferability and reusability properties.

Figure 2. Cell information of hex-grid input layer for *Aedes albopictus* occurrence in GAMA.

3. Conclusion and Outlook

This paper proposes a workflow that couples a Geospatial Knowledge Graph with an agent-based model for spatially explicit vector-borne disease risk modelling, using *Aedes albopictus* and dengue as a use case. The GeoKG acts as a semantic pre-processing layer that integrates heterogeneous environmental, demographic, and ecological data, formalises them through a shared ontology, and exposes them to the ABM via a hexagonal DGGs. Compared with conventional layer-based environments, the approach offers explicit ontology-driven semantics for risk-area definitions, ontology reusability across areas of interest, and traceability of model inputs through structured provenance.

Immediate next steps are the integration of further environmental and demographic datasets, the implementation of the ontology following Consoli et al. (2025) and Xiao et al. (2025), and the validation of the habitat representation against occurrence data independent of the records used in the graph construction. Long-term tasks cover the inclusion of vulnerability indicators to the Exposure \times Hazard scope, moving toward a full operationalisation of risk as conventionally defined. The separation of concerns is preserved: behavioural rules and emergent dynamics remain in the ABM, while the GeoKG continues to specify *what* the environment is, with the additional capacity to expose state- and context-dependent relations at runtime rather than only at initialisation.

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